

Recall Plots

Dataset

Clinician

Expert

Full-text

Distal radius fractures approach

Distal radius fractures closed reduction

Hallux valgus prognostic

Dataset

Clinician

Expert

Full-text

Head and neck cancer bone

Head and neck cancer imaging

Obstetric emergency training

Dataset

Clinician

Expert

Full-text

Post intensive care treatment

Pregnancy medication

Shoulder replacement diagnostic

Dataset

Clinician

Expert

Full-text

Shoulder replacement surgery

Shoulder dystocia positioning

Shoulder dystocia recurrence

Dataset

Clinician

Expert

Full-text

Total knee replacement

Vascular access

